

Ride 2Rail

D5.2 MAAS ASSESSMENT TOOL

This project has received funding from the Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 881825

Project Acronym	Ride2Rail
Starting date	01/12/2019
Duration (in months)	36
Deliverable number	D5.2
Call Identifier	S2R-OC-IP4-01-2019
GRANT Agreement no	881825
Due date of the Deliverable	30/11/2021
Actual submission date	18/02/2022
Responsible/Author	UNEW
Dissemination level	PU
Work package	WP5
Main editor	David Golightly
Reviewer(s)	CERTH, UIC
Status of document (draft/issued)	ISSUED

Reviewed: Yes

Consortium of partners

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METROPOLIA	Finland

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Revision	Date	Description
0.1	08/02/2022	Draft submitted to contributors for comments
0.2	15/02/2022	Minor edits in response to reviews
1.0	18/02/2022	Final version submitted to consortium

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The aim of this deliverable is describe the usability approach for use in WP5 and for Ride2Rail as a whole. In order to meet this aim, a number of objectives are covered:

1. Scoping what is meant by usability
2. Understand common tools for measuring usability, and particularly those that have previous application for MaaS or shared mobility
3. Identify an appropriate delivery format (in this case, and online survey)
4. Build demonstrator online survey

The documents reviews five approaches – System Usability Scale, Technology Acceptance Model, Software Usability Measurement Index, NASA-TLX and User Experience Questionnaire. These are contrasted for their relevance to the aims and technical capabilities of Ride2Rail. The proposed usability approach is to deliver the System Usability Scale (SUS), adapted to Ride2Rail along with two open questions on perceptions of usability, and a best-worst scaling to confirm user preferences for trip criteria. These questions will be delivered as a sub-section of the KPI survey that will be submitted in support of Task 5.3. This survey will be delivered using Online Surveys, a GDPR-compliant tool. An example of the potential survey page is shown in the Appendix.

Abbreviations and acronyms

CFM	Call For Members
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
IT	Information Technology
IP	Innovation Programme
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NASA-TLX	NASA-Task Load Index
R2R	Ride2Rail
SUMI	Software Usability Measurement Inventory
SUS	System Usability Scale
T	Task
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
TC	Travel Companion
UEQ	User Experience Questionnaire
WP	Work Package

1. BACKGROUND

Shift2Rail context

Shift2Rail is the first European rail initiative to seek focused research and innovation and market-driven solutions by accelerating the integration of new and advanced technologies into innovative rail product solutions. Shift2Rail promotes the competitiveness of the European rail industry and meets changing EU transport needs. Research carried out under this Horizon 2020 initiative develops the necessary technology to complete the Single European Railway Area.

The delivery of Shift2Rail is based around five Innovation Programmes (IPs); the focus of this report is IP4 - IT solutions for attractive rail services. To become a more attractive option, rail must respond to customer needs to support anytime, anywhere, door-to-door, intermodal journeys encompassing distinct modes of transportation. Rail must achieve interoperability with other transport modes and mobility services, with regions, cities and people engaged in social and economic activities, and with the key elements of the supply chains which can make rail products and services available to those people. In order to achieve this, rail needs to take due advantage of the increasing connectivity of people and objects, the availability of European Global Navigation Satellite System-based locations, the advances in cloud computing, big, linked and open data and the propagation of internet and social media. The step towards sharing data needs to be considered and progressively developed, in order to enable service developers to provide connected travellers with the services they need and expect.

Ride2Rail

A key aspect of delivering more attractive services is by delivering end-to-end (or first- and last-mile) travel services that enable rail as their core mode of mobility. This can be challenging in a rural environment, where connectivity to rail is problematic. It is also relevant in urban or peri-urban environments where there may be poorer provision of public transit or congestion of roads.

Contributing to Shift2Rail's IP4, Ride2Rail's overall objective is to develop an innovative framework for intelligent mobility, facilitating the efficient combination of flexible (ridesharing) and scheduled transport services (rail, bus, and other public transport services), thus enhancing the performance of the overall mobility system. Ride2Rail should, in particular, address the first and last mile problem by offering a wider range of transit options, while harnessing the capacity of single occupancy vehicles, along with existing, or future, demand responsive transit.

Ride2Rail aims to integrate multiple (public/private/social) data sets and existing transport platforms for promoting an effective ride sharing practice of citizens, making it a complementary transport mode that extends public transport networks.

The objectives of the Ride2Rail project are:

- To develop an innovative framework for intelligent mobility, facilitating efficient combination of flexible and scheduled transport services, integrating real-time information about public transport and ride sharing;
- To facilitate the comparison and the choice between multiple options/services classified by a set of criteria, for example environmental, travel time, comfort, cost;
- To encourage carpooling (and ride sharing acceptance) as complementary for public transport;
- To enhance the performance of the overall mobility system, reducing road congestion and environmental impact, reinforcing the mobility offer in rural and low-demand areas;
- To combine travel offer classifications and software components, integrating them into existing collective and on-demand transport services;
- To induct the access to high-capacity services thanks to easy-to-use multimodal and integrated travel planning, booking, ticketing and payment features;
- To design, develop and test in four real demonstrators a set of software components for the IP4 ecosystem, including an enhanced Travel Companion and the crowd-based Transport Service Provider;
- To produce recommendations for replicability.

Work Package 5 context

The project will implement demonstrations of the Ride2Rail service in four locations – Padua, Italy; Athens, Greece; Brno, Czech Republic; Helsinki, Finland. A critical aspect of these demonstrations is to understand their performance against the aims of the project, and in terms of supporting sustainability actions in these locations.

Work package 5 of Ride2Rail sets out the evaluation activities for Ride2Rail. Specifically, it draws upon the definition of KPIs (defined in Work package 4) and uses these as evaluation targets. Figure 1 illustrates the flow of tasks in WP5. T5.1 specifies the nature of KPI measurement by understanding the feasibility of different measurement techniques. T5.3 will actively measure the KPIs during demo execution in WP4. Ultimately, the KPIs will be used to inform the impact analysis for Ride2Rail (as calculated in T5.4). These impact areas are:

1. increase the number of multi-occupancy vehicle trips, as opposed to single occupancy-vehicle trips;
2. increase access to public transit for users in a rural and/or suburban setting;
3. contribute to minimising emissions.

In parallel, T5.2 sets out usability assessment criteria for Ride2Rail. This document covers these usability assessment criteria.

Figure 1: *Task Flow for WP5*

2. OBJECTIVES AND SCOPE

Deliverable objectives

The aim of this deliverable is to describe the usability approach for use in WP5 and for Ride2Rail as a whole.

In order to meet this aim, a number of objectives are covered:

1. Scoping what is meant by usability;
2. Understand common tools for measuring usability, and particularly those that have previous application for MaaS or shared mobility;
3. Identify an appropriate delivery format (in this case, an online survey);
4. Build demonstrator online survey.

Scope

Scope and assumptions are as follows:

- The usability tool should cover all aspects of the Ride2Rail ICT user experience. This includes both passengers using the enhanced S2R travel companion, and users of the driver companion.
- The usability tool should be suitable for use in the four demo sites: Athens, Brno, Helsinki and Padua.
- The usability tool may embody additional questions that support understanding of usage patterns.
- Data from the usability tool may be supplemented by additional user data gathering – for example through focus groups or interviews conducted within the execution of task T5.3. This nature and design of this additional user data gathering is out of scope for the current document.

Inputs and outputs

Inputs

WP3 provides the technical functions and integration that will be evaluated in WP5. Therefore, the usability approach for T5.2 must reflect the technical capabilities that users will engage with while experiencing the Ride2Rail service.

WP4 provides the demo context where Ride2Rail will be evaluated. This covers both the contextual factors (such as the types of trips likely to be encountered in a demo area) as well as the capacity for demo site leaders to support evaluation activities, which influences the feasibility of evaluation and therefore the delivery mechanism for the usability tool.

D5.1 has proposed the delivery mechanism of the monitoring approach. In order to minimise the effort of participants (and therefore increase the likelihood of responding), and usability approach should be closely aligned with the KPI monitoring approach.

In response to feedback during the process of T5.2, the usefulness of trip offer categories has been suggested as an element of the usability survey. Therefore, the trip offer categories identified in WP2 and implemented in WP3 have been used to supplement the usability tool.

Outputs

- The direct output of T5.2 is T5.3 which will monitor demo performance.
- Subsequently, T5.4 will use those measures to make impact evaluation.

3. RELEVANCE OF USABILITY

Role of usability

Combining the capabilities and constraints of mobile technology in an effective manner makes for a seamless experience and a powerful mobility tool. Technology has to be fit for purpose in order to deliver its promised impact. An important component of being fit for purpose is making sure technology offers its intended target audience (or ‘users’) the functionality they require in a manner that is appropriate to how they want to achieve their goals. This quality is commonly referred to as usability – “The extent to which a product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use”(ISO DIS 9241-210). Usability ensures that people will have the objective outcomes of greater productivity, better efficiency, and fewer errors, while having the subjective experience of greater confidence and satisfaction in terms of achieving set goals, and a greater propensity to re-use a product.

Usability is a general term, widely used within the role of ICT (and beyond). It is also a key and underpinning aspect of the more general term “user experience”(UX) – where usability combines with factors such as the emotional appeal and the findability of a service (Hassenzahl and Tractsinsky, 2006).

An application that is easy to learn will require less training, less support and less time until it plays a productive role in the user’s work. As important as supporting the complete novice, ease of use supports those users who may only use an application infrequently. Norman (1988) lists a number of characteristics that make a device easy to learn.

- Visibility – whereby the user can tell the state of application, and also quickly see what functionality is available, with the most important functions being most prominent, as opposed to ordered alphabetically, arbitrarily or by which service provides the highest revenue to an operator. What is important may vary from context to another and must be carefully understood before making a design decision (this work has been conducted for Ride2Rail within WP2). Visibility does not have to be literal – the structure of interaction should be made clear, even when working with audio-based menus (Howell et al, 2006).
- A conceptual model – users will try to build a model of how the various elements of a device or application fit together so they can make assumptions about how it will work and predict either its actions, or responses to user inputs. The application should therefore present a coherent model of how all the aspects of the functionality work together, so the user is informed by accurate information, rather than guesswork. Conversely, only those aspects of the system that the user needs to actively engage with should be salient to the user. The power of a strong conceptual model has been demonstrated repeatedly to enhance learning of a device. Consistency is also critical to this; the application should be internally consistent (similar names, icons etc. mean similar things and do similar things), but should also be consistent with other applications on the same device, and with other technology and terminology.
- Good mappings – there should be a clear relationship between actions and their effects, so that it is clear what the outcome will be once the user makes a choice. This allows the user to guess an outcome with certainty rather than making an error or having to refer to some form of support.

- Feedback – The application should provide information about itself in a timely manner (see ‘Performance’, below) and in a manner that makes sense to the user. Error messages and dialogs should be clear and concise.
- Efficiency – While ease of use can get the user started with their interaction, it is also important that the user’s interaction is efficient. The limited screen size and input mechanisms of handheld devices means that some interactions needs many more sequential steps than might be expected on a desktop. Examining the complexity of the application (at design or procurement stage) is critical to ensure the application is as efficient to use as possible.
- Furthermore, efficiency can be viewed as both intrinsic and extrinsic factors. *Intrinsic* factors means factors such as those above that relate to the ease with which an application can be used (how many clicks, how quickly it responds). *Extrinsic* factors means how well the functionality of the application matches the purpose for which it is being used – for example, does the app make it easy to request a journey. In the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) Venkatesh and Davis (2000) distinguish between the ‘ease of use’ and the ‘usefulness’ of a software product or service. Both are required for overall product acceptance.

Usability in the context of shared mobility services

A review of early on-demand lift sharing technologies (Levofsky and Greenberg, 2001) found the basic usability of a number of schemes was a major barrier to their adoption, and an evaluation of a live lift share deployment (Sharples et al., 2012) found significant issues with the presentation of maps and routes, and difficulties for users in understanding the privacy model provided by the technology. Subsequent proposals for lift sharing technology have highlighted considerations such as the structure required to submit matching requests (Dailey et al., 1999; Wash et al, 2005), the availability of chat-like functionality (Brereton and Ghelewat, 2010) to finesse trips and build trust, and the use of multiple platforms (Wash et al., 2005) as important design considerations for lift sharing technology (see also Golightly et al., 2019).

There needs to be an accurate reflection of not only the availability of the travel mode, but of the economic / sharing form, and the functions of the service in the design of the online service, and increasingly it must be adapted to the needs of the smartphone. This clarity of purpose can be undermined when there is more than one competing service within a given area. Morency (2007) found this to be the case with rideshare schemes.

Usability extends beyond the functionality of ordering a trip. The mobile app is overwhelmingly the most common way to register and pay for shared travel services, and this is an aspect of the service that is often overlooked (Feng et al., 2020). Jahanshahi i et al (2019) and Fishman et al (2015) found usability factors for a shared bike scheme included specific concerns around the ease of registration. A lack of clarity around features such as smart routing, registration or peer-to-peer coordination have proved to be significant barriers to shared travel app adoption (Sharples et al., 2012; Adele and Dionisio, 2020) and comprise part of the overall ‘friction’ of using a service which may impede uptake (Lamberton and Rose, 2012). However, it may be possible to encourage sustainable mobility by presenting information that can encourage a sustainable trip choice, such as identifying routes that are safe or more comfortable for cyclists (Golightly et al., 2018). This is important given that purely rational motivations (i.e., cost and time) have limited

impact on moving people out of private cars and into alternative sustainable modes, and demonstrating the affective and aspirational benefits of modal alternatives is seen to be critical to mode shift (Steg, 2005; Sjoman et al., 2020).

Finally, the usability of shared travel and rideshare in particular must be viewed as a dynamic process. Sharples et al (2012) highlight that users go through multiple stages of trial and error and practicing use, before becoming comfortable with the functionality of shared travel. The usability of a shared travel app must therefore support users in exploration and becoming familiar with the shared travel functionality and requirements, if it is to lead to a more permanent behaviour change.

4. APPROACH

The approach taken to identify a suitable methodology for assessing usability is as follows.

- 1) A number of preexisting usability tools exist. The literature reviews identified these tools and in particular those that had previously been used for ride sharing applications.
- 2) Tools were reviewed from the literature and assessed in terms of their general suitability, and their specific suitability for Ride2Rail.
- 3) Potential delivery mechanisms were also assessed based on factors such as access to participants, ease of implementation and GDPR.
- 4) A draft form of the usability tools, for application in Ride2Rail, was developed.
- 5) To validate the outputs of each of the above stages, a consultation document was written and circulated to relevant Ride2Rail partners. This document was used to elicit feedback on the proposed options and delivery mechanism.

Figure 2 shows these steps as a flow diagram.

Figure 2: Flow of usability method identification

The remainder of this deliverable describes the outcomes of Steps 1-4. Feedback resulting from Step 5 has been integrated into the relevant sections. This included the best-worst

analysis of journey criteria, and the preference to have local translations of the usability tool at demo locations.

5. STEP 1: IDENTIFY USABILITY TOOL CONTENT

Usability measure *content* refers to the questions being asked, and the data collected, from the usability approach. A number of options exist for the content of the usability approach. These range from very open-ended questions, through to standardised usability scales and user experience scales. Usability / user experience scales have the advantage of being standardised and previously trialled by other studies. Some of these usability / user experience scales have been used in other car share or Mobility as a Service settings (e.g. Wright et al., 2020).

The following potential tools were identified

System Usability Scale – The System Usability Scale (SUS) is a common usability measure (Brooke, 1996; Brooke, 2013). The tool comprises of a 10 item, 5 point Likert scale. Items are weighted in terms of both negative and positive responses. The scale is widely used and has been adapted multiple times to fit multiple contexts. Furthermore, the SUS has been benchmarked, with an overall SUS score of 80% or above being an indicator of high usability (Bangor et al., 2009). Finally, SUS has been used on multiple occasions in the analysis of mobility solutions (e.g. Laine et al., 2020, including ride sharing (e.g. Sila et al., 2021), such as in its application for the assessment of SocialCar (Wright et al., 2020).

Table 1 gives an example of SUS.

	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	Slightly Agree	Strongly Agree
I think that I would like to use this system frequently.					
I found the system unnecessarily complex.					
I thought the system was easy to use.					
I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.					
I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.					
I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.					
I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.					
I found the system very cumbersome to use.					
I felt very confident using the system.					

I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.					
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Table 1: System Usability Scale

Technology Acceptance Model – The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a common tool to assess both usefulness and ease-of-use of a technology. Originally based on the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Davis, 1989), the TAM underpins a usability survey tool. The common form is a 12-item scale though there are many variations (e.g. Venkatesh and Davis, 2000; Kaasinen et al., 2011). TAM is extremely widely used and benchmarked. TAM has had some application with ride share-type applications (e.g. Min et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2020; Akbari et al., 2021). For an example see Figure 3.

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is designed to give you an opportunity to rate this product's usefulness and ease-of-use.

To as great an extent as possible, think about all the tasks that you do with the product while you answer these questions.

Please read each statement and indicate how strongly you agree or disagree with the statement. Please read the statements carefully, but don't spend a lot of time on each item -- your first impression is fine.

Note that for this questionnaire (TAM), all items have a positive tone so greater levels of agreement (to the left of the scale) indicate a better user experience.

1. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements.

	Extremely agree	Quite agree	Slightly agree	Neither	Slightly disagree	Quite disagree	Extremely disagree
1. Using this product in my job enables me to accomplish tasks more quickly than other products in its class.	☐						
2. Using this product improves my job performance.	☐						
3. Using this product in my job increases my productivity.	☐						
4. Using this product enhances my effectiveness on the job.	☐						
5. Using this product makes it easier to do my job.	☐						
6. I have found this product useful in my job.	☐						
7. Learning to operate this product was easy for me.	☐						
8. I found it easy to get this product to do what I want it to do.	☐						
9. My interaction with this product has been clear and understandable.	☐						
10. I found this product to be flexible to interact with.	☐						
11. It was easy for me to become skillful at using this product.	☐						
12. I found this product easy to use.	☐						

Figure 3: TAM Taken from Lewis (2019).

System Usability Measurement Index – The System Usability Measurement Index (SUMI) (Kirakowski and Corbett, 1993) is a multi-item scale. It addresses a number of aspects of usability including efficiency, affect, helpfulness, control learnability. It has wide application

but has not penetrated into usability practice to the degree of TAM or SUS. This is in part due to research users needing to obtain a license to use the scale. There are no known applications of SUMI for mobility, MaaS or ridesharing type applications.

NASA Task Load Index - The NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) is a very common tool for assessing the workload associated with using a particular system or technology, or when engaged in a particular task. There are some variations but the primary version is a six item scale covering mental demand, physical demand, temporal demand, performance, effort and frustration (see Figure 4). While very common in human factors, and some Human-Computer Interaction applications, it has little visible use specifically for mobility, MaaS and rideshare applications. Furthermore, it must be used almost immediately after the completion of the task.

Figure 4: NASA-TLX Taken from Hart (2006, October).

User Experience Questionnaire - User Experience (UX) is a multi-faceted concept that covers not only usability, but affective elements and aspects such as findability and accessibility (Hassenzahl and Tractinsky, 2006). The User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) (Schrepp et al., 2017) encapsulates the main aspects of UX, over 8 dimensions. Variations of UEQ have been used in a number of settings, including mobility (Gabrielli et al., 2014), electric car design (Dupont et al., 2019) and aspects of shared travel such as shuttlebus information design (Mirnig et al., 2019). An example of the UEQ is presented in Figure 5.

obstructive	o o o o o o o	supportive
complicated	o o o o o o o	easy
inefficient	o o o o o o o	efficient
confusing	o o o o o o o	clear
boring	o o o o o o o	exiting
not interesting	o o o o o o o	interesting
conventional	o o o o o o o	inventive
usual	o o o o o o o	leading edge

Figure 5: User Experience Questionnaire From Schrepp et al (2017)

6. STEP 2: USABILITY TOOL SELECTION

Primary survey tool

Table 2 gives an overview of each of the identified tools, along with their benefits and the drawbacks for each tool for usage in the Ride2Rail context. Based on this analysis, and also considering some of the mechanisms for delivery (see Section 8) there are clear advantages for using the System Usability Scale. It is short, flexible, and widely benchmarked. This is proposed as the primary usability assessment tool.

Tool	Description	Advantages	Disadvantages
System Usability Scale (Brook, 1996)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10-item Likert Scaling • Covers aspect such as ease of use, ease of learning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Widely used • Very flexible • Validated benchmarks of scores (Bangor et al., 2009) • Can be used at the time but also as an end of demonstration assessment • Has been used in MaaS and shared travel settings (e.g. social car [Wright et al., 2020]) therefore specific benchmarks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Somewhat simplistic • Not strongly theoretically driven
Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989) [See appendix 6.2]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Common version is 12-item scale. Covers Ease-of-use and usefulness. • Many variations of the scale (e.g. Venkatesh and Davis, 2000; Kaasinen et al., 2011) • Based on Theory of Planned Behaviour 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Covers core usability concepts • Extremely widely used and benchmarked (Lee et al., 2003) • Theoretically-driven – in a manner that indicates potential future use • Has been used in shared travel contexts, therefore specific benchmarks • Can be used at the time but also as an end of demonstration assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slightly longer than System Usability Scale and therefore pushes up total length of survey • More of an orientation to work tools
System Usability Measurement Index (Kirakowski)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Common multi item scale 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Covers multiple dimensions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficiency • Affect • Helpfulness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not used in the MaaS / shared travel space – therefore no benchmark

and Corbett, 1993) [Not publically available]		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control • Learnability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possibly too many dimensions (and items) for a short flexible survey
NASA-TLX workload scale (Hart and Staveland, 1988 [See Appendix 6.3])	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very common workload tool • Assesses workload across multiple dimensions • Validated in a number of contexts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extremely widely used in general usability work and in human factors • Good benchmarking for general applications • Highly validated • Short to administer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not used in the MaaS / shared travel space - therefore no benchmark • Several items (eg Physical workload) are not relevant • Must be administered soon after use (eg minutes) for maximum effect
User Experience Questionnaire (Schrepp et al., 2017 [See Appendix 6.4])	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most common user experience questionnaire • Based around hedonic and pragmatic considerations of User Experience • Conforms with Hassenzahl and Tractinsky (2006) UX model 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-faceted • Short version is easy to complete 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not used in the MaaS / shared travel space - therefore no benchmark • Not strictly usability - includes other aspects of experience • Difficult to delineate how much of scoring linked to the app usability, and how much general experience of Ride2Rail / Shift2Rail

Table 2: Comparison of usability measures

Free text questions

In addition, free text fields can capture any additional detailed comments. Rather than simply adding a free text box, a structured approach can encourage more feedback. It is common practice to ask “What is the best thing about your experience?” “What is the worst thing about your experience?” This approach is useful for eliciting both negative and positive comments from user who either like, or dislike, the experience.

Trip selection preferences

Finally, WP2 has identified a number of criteria that are important user considerations for trip selection (Table 3). These 11 criteria will be offered to the user in the Ride2Rail enhanced travel companion app to assist in trip matching. In order to assess the usefulness

of trip categories, it is useful to confirm at the end of the demo period, which of the criteria are most helpful in selecting trips. Therefore, a short section will ask users what was the most useful offer categories for trip selection. The criteria will be assessed using a “Best-Worst” scaling approach. This approach allows respondents to rate items based on their perceptions of ranking of items from “best” to “worst” (Finn and Louviere, 1992). This approach has been widely used in a range of sectors (eg healthcare [Flynn et al., 2007]) and has been successfully used in mobility as a service research (e.g. Polydoropoulou et al., 2020).

The **Quick** category measures how convenient and efficient the solution is in terms of time-related issues, considering the total travel time, the waiting time between legs and the number of stops required. If the solution includes a segment on-road (e.g., bus/car) and real-time data on traffic congestion are available, also these data can be taken into account.

The **Reliable** category concerns the likelihood of delays, traffic congestion, breakdowns or last-minute changes that could affect the travel time and comfort of the trip. Some solutions are inherently variable (e.g. traffic delays when crossing a city at rush hour), while other solutions might offer a small window to change the mode of transport that could cause massive idle times. For this reason, also the frequency of the service for involved solutions should be taken into account. Lastly, the influence of the weather on the trip is taken into account.

The **Cheap** category concerns the total price of a trip, the possibility of sharing part of it with others and the ease of payment, giving additional value to solutions that offer an integrated fare system and do not require the user to purchase different tickets from different platforms.

The **Comfortable** category concerns objective factors such as the number of interchanges required or the possibility of having a comfortable seat but also covers a set of other elements about the quality of the trip that has to be evaluated through users’ feedback. Relevant factors are the cleanliness of the stations and vehicles used and the feeling of personal safety.

The **Door-to-door** category covers the distance of the user’s start and endpoint from the beginning and destination locations of the solution provided. It is measured by the amount of walking or driving distance the user has to cover.

The **Environmentally Friendly** category covers the green aspects of the trip, taking into account at least the amount of CO₂ emissions measured per kilometre/traveller for each mean of transport included in the Offer and considering the distance covered and the number of passengers. If available, additional determinant factors can be considered as the energy consumption, the NOx emissions (nitrogen oxides) and the carbon footprint.

The **Short** category focuses on minimizing the distance covered.

The **Multitasking** category concerns the extent to which the user can perform other tasks while travelling. These activities can regard productivity (personal or work), fitness, or enjoyment. This category considers the amount of space available, the presence of silence or business area, as well as whether the internet connection and/or plugs are provided. Lastly, the level of privacy might

also influence the extent to which a person can work and could be considered as a determinant factor for this category.

The **Social** category concerns the maximization of the number of people the user will share the trip with and his/her ability to network or socialize based on the context and means used. Moreover, it takes into account solutions that contribute to social causes or involves volunteering or charity activities (e.g., donations).

The **Panoramic** category promotes solutions passing through beautiful landscapes (like a particular village or a forest) or historical sites. This category also takes into account the usual sightseeing itineraries for tourists to promote solutions passing near monuments or other interesting spots.

The **Healthy** category concerns the involvement of walking and/or cycling in an offer.

Table 3: *Trip offer categories*

7. STEP 3: USABILITY DELIVERY FORMAT

After discussion with WP3 and WP4 leaders (see D5.1; D4.3) regarding the feasibility of different measurement approaches for KPIs, the following constraints on the delivery mechanism have been identified:

- There is currently no facility to include “point in time” usability assessments (e.g. micro-surveys after each trip (Cranwell et al., 2015); at the end of each day) within the R2R ecosystem (e.g. through the driver companion); indeed, any inclusion of surveys within the Ride2Rail ecosystem would be difficult (and impossible for aspects provided by CFM).
- A survey methodology is required to capture KPI-relevant information (T5.1). This could also be used to deliver usability assessment.

Based on the above options, and given the technical constraints of the project and requirements of demo partners, the preferred option is a single online survey sent to each participant at the end of the demo period is the preferred option. This survey can be embedded within the planned KPI survey.

‘Online Surveys’ (<https://www.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/>) is proposed as the survey tool. It is GDPR compliant, UNew has a license, and links can be sent to WP4 / demo partners for distribution. UNew can then process responses, without requiring any personal or identifying information, and thus remain within GDPR compliance. Online Survey has logic functionality – based on user responses it is possible to take users down a specific survey route. For example, if users have used the driver companion they can answer a separate set of questions relating to the usability of that function.

Currently the KPI survey (including demographic element) is short – approximately 3 minutes, and is therefore able to absorb additional questions without impact to participant experience (Hoerger, 2010). Recording usability in the same survey as recording KPI information has some clear advantages.

- o Responses to KPIs can be co-analysed with usability measures (e.g. do people who rate usability more highly also take more trips?).
- o The survey will also include a brief demographics section – therefore usability can also be assessed by demographic groups (e.g. do younger users prefer the usability of Ride2Rail?).

8. STEP 4: EARLY VERSION OF USABILITY TOOL

The usability survey, based on SUS, will be embedded in the KPI survey distributed to demo participants. One issue raised in the consultation for the usability survey was the need to distinguish between:

- those users who used the driver companion (offering trips as drivers),
- those who used the enhanced ride2rail travel companion (requesting trips as passengers),
- those users who used both aspects during the demo.

The assumption is that only passengers will use the travel companion component, and therefore driver-only users do not need to respond to the best worst Trip Offer section. Therefore the logic of the survey is as follows in Figure 6 – sections relevant to usability are highlighted in white. Usability sections completed by different user groups will be as follows :

- Passenger only – Travel companion SUS questions, trip offer best-worst scaling, open questions
- Driver only – Driver companion SUS questions, open questions
- Driver and Passenger – Driver companion SUS questions, Travel companion SUS questions, trip offer best-worst scaling, open questions

The appendix includes draft versions of the three forms of survey – one for drivers only, one for passengers only and one for users who are both drivers and passengers. **Please Note** Wording around the introductory text for questions is draft and only for guidance at this time.

Figure 6: Survey design

9. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable has described the proposed usability approach for assessing the usability of the Ride2Rail service. The proposed usability approach is to deliver the System Usability Scale (SUS), adapted to Ride2Rail along with two open questions on perceptions of usability, and a best-worst scaling to confirm user preferences for trip criteria.

These questions will be delivered as a sub-section of the KPI survey that will be submitted in support of Task 5.3. An example of the potential survey page is shown in the Appendix.

Next steps (i.e. to be conducted within T5.3 to ensure the full usability assessment process).

1. Develop full survey
2. Send for translation in relevant demo partner languages
3. Deploy at relevant demo sites
4. Align with any additional data collection activities taking place in WP4
5. Analyse and report

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11. APPENDIX

Usability page 1 - Usage selection

Service options

Which did you use during the demo period?

- Just the travel companion (I only tried to be a passenger)
- Just the driver companion (I only tried to be a driver)
- Both a passenger and a driver

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System Usability Component (passenger version, also available as driver companion version)

	Strongly agree	Slightly agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Slightly disagree	Strongly disagree
I think that I would like to use the Ride2Rail frequently.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I found the Ride2Rail unnecessarily complex.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I thought the Ride2Rail was easy to use.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use the Ride2Rail.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I found the various functions in the Ride2Rail were well integrated.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I thought there was too much inconsistency in this Ride2Rail.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I would imagine that most people would learn to use the Ride2Rail very quickly.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I found the Ride2Rail very cumbersome to use.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I felt very confident using the Ride2Rail.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with the Ride2Rail.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

General Usability Section (passenger version, also available as driver companion version)

Are there any other ways to choose your journey?

What is the best thing about the Ride2Rail service? What did you like about it?

What problems did you face with the Ride2Rail service? What did you dislike about it?

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Trip Offer Best-Worst Ranking (Passenger only)

Which of these options are most useful when organising a trip (1 is MOST useful, 11 is LEAST useful)

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Quick	☐										
Reliable	☐										
Cheap	☐										
Comfortable	☐										
Door-to-door	☐										
Environmentally friendly	☐										
Short	☐										
Multitasking	☐										
Social	☐										
Panoramic	☐										
Healthy	☐										

Are there any other ways to choose your journey?